

IP4MaaS

Deliverable D 6.1 Assessment Methodology

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1. Executive Summary

The IP4MaaS Project aims at demonstrating the benefits of Innovation Programme 4 (IP4) through pilot demonstrators of collective and shared mobility services in six different European countries' cities: Athens, Barcelona, Padua, Liberec, Osijek, and Warsaw. The technologies have been created within IP4 Shift2 Rail Joint Undertaking (S2R JU), developed within the COHESIVE¹ project and tackle various aspects of traveller experience, meaning the interoperability of Transport Service Providers' (TSPs) services, travel shopping, booking & ticketing, trip tracking, travel companion technologies and business analytics.

IP4MaaS outcomes will impact on existing complementary projects COHESIVE, ExtenSive and CONNECTIVE² as well as on the CFM project MaaSive³, aiming at developing passenger service platform specifications for an enhanced multi-modal transport eco-system including Mobility as a Service (MaaS). The relevant expected impact of this complementary topic is related to the integration of urban sprawl underpinned by the opportunities that the digitalization of transport e.g., MaaS brings. This is particularly relevant for the implementation of truly user-centric services for co-modality in multimodal journeys integrating public transport, shared mobility, micro-mobility as well as private and on demand approaches.

IP4MaaS has adopted an iterative approach for the demonstrations. There are two iterations, C-REL (Core Release) and F-REL (Final Release). The first iteration initially involved Padua, Athens and Barcelona, due though to limitations from CFMs' side and technical limitations from certain TSPs side, it involved only Athens, while the second iteration will include all demonstration locations.

This document constitutes the Deliverable D6.1 "Assessment Methodology", which aims to provide common tools for the cross-site evaluation of performance and impacts of IP4MAAS demo sites activities, by means of both performance assessment and impact assessment. In order to collect and validate the data in "AS IS" and "TO BE" situations, the local evaluation plans with related Key Performance Indicators selected and procedures will be presented.

The evaluation of project outcomes as well as validation work and data collection will be based on the methodology related to performance valuation as well as impact and process evaluation. Since demo sites could experience difficulties data collections procedures, the methodology will be flexible, with continuous monitoring and redefinitions if needed. However, to assure homogeneity, a stable baseline for the data already collected will be maintained.

The document starts with the present introductory section, followed by the project background and the description of the overall evaluation objectives (sections 5 and 6).

In section 7 the overall evaluation approach is presented, identifying type of data, target groups and criteria for selecting Key Performance Indicators.

In section 8, the performance evaluation framework is presented, including the methodology used to create the dataset, the algorithms used for the computational analysis and the methodology

¹ https://projects.shift2rail.org/s2r_ip4_n.aspx?p=COHESIVE

² https://projects.shift2rail.org/s2r_ip4_n.aspx?p=CONNECTIVE

³ https://projects.shift2rail.org/s2r_ip4_n.aspx?p=MaaSive

used to calculate the efficiency rate.

In section 9 it is described the impact assessment, including the Macro-model designed for quantifying socio-economic and environmental impacts and related preliminary KPIs.

Finally, section 10 provides final commentaries and next steps of the evaluation process.

2. Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
CFM	Calls for Members
DL	Dissemination and exploitation leader
DoA	Description of the Action
EL	Ethical leader
EU	European Union
FS	Financial Statement
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OC	Open Call
PC	Project coordinator
PM	Project manager
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
QAC	Quality Assurance Committee
S2R JU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
TL	Technical leader
TSP	Transport Service Provider
USI	User satisfaction Index
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work package leader

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5. Background

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D6.1 “Assessment Methodology” in the framework of the W6, Task 6.1 of the IP4MaaS project (S2R-OC-IP4-01-2020, GA 101015492).

Mobility as a Service (MaaS) is a mobility distribution model in which one single integrated service provider allows customer’s major transportation needs to meet. MaaS provides a new way of thinking in terms of how the delivery and consumption of mobility is organized and managed. Based on multiple modes of transport on a one-stop-shop principle, it aims to provide consumers with flexible, efficient, user-oriented and ecological mobility services.

MaaS is a tool that might change the ways in which people plan their travels and it could influence the emerging trends that will affect the future of transportation. The rise of sharing economy allows to extent the “as a service” paradigm to the ITS technologies sector, which recently has had important advances. Specifically, MaaS aims to get over the car ownership model as well as the current market fragmentations, exploiting the integration between different means of transport and networks through combined mobility packages. Therefore, the modal shift from privately owned and operated cars to the use of shared resources and public transportation is driven by MaaS and the substitution of privately-owned cars, highly underutilized, with various forms of mobility services will be the final achievement, with lower environmental footprint and higher asset utilisation as further side effects.

The always more demanding and fragmented users’ needs and expectations can be addressed by the new technologies, while the resources for developing transport systems are decreasing. An easy access to mobility at urban and suburban level as well as well-functioning and seamless transport services (where transport is lived as an “experience”) are an example of users’ different needs that smart and personalized mobility services have to address, allowing MaaS to achieve a paradigm change in transportation. MaaS is all about sharing mobility, integrated booking/ticketing/payment, multimodal passenger transport, multimodal traveller information, etc. Private sharing mobility services, public/private parking, scheduled public transport services, and on-demand public transport services are just few of the different mobility services that feed the MaaS.

Instead of a technically-focused regulation of individual transport modes, the public sector, which can build a regulative framework acting as an enabler, should aim to ensure transparent market conditions where users (as consumers) have a secure legal position.

Providing smarter transport connections for all sectors, profitable markets for new transport services, renewing opportunities for the traditional transport business sectors as part of innovative services concepts could be just few of the many benefits which the development of MaaS may generate; it constitutes the integration of various forms of transport services into a single mobility service accessible on demand.

Another aim to achieve is a more convenient, sustainable and even cheaper alternative to the private use of the car in order to give the best value proposition for users. A MaaS system open to all service providers and inclusive for all different kind of users is the offer that the design and development of a MaaS ecosystem should produce, respecting the principle of openness and inclusivity.

To reduce the ownership and use of private cars and by that reduce the traffic congestion, emissions and parking problems are the main objectives of MaaS in urban areas. To reach these

objectives, the inclusion of all the available transport modes in the service coverage is the most effective way. MaaS services can be offered to both private consumers and company employees. The improvement of service levels (i.e., trams, buses, subway), through the integration of public transport with taxis and other modes of demand-responsive transport, is the focus of MaaS in suburban areas, which are also suitable locations for carpooling and ride-sharing, according with the availability of platforms for managing and effective tools. Because of lack of connections to scheduled services, in rural areas MaaS services are equivalent to the desired services in suburban areas.

From the operational feasibility viewpoint, MaaS development might influences the parties involved in transport and mobility service provision. From the technical feasibility viewpoint, the most important elements of the MaaS concept real-life implementation are the design, operation and maintenance of MaaS system. Information technology integration as well as infrastructure and equipment integration are the main technical elements to consider for the successful development of MaaS. From the economic feasibility viewpoint, transport operators and mobility service providers have complex fare structures which should be analysed to define and implement a potential one payment system within the MaaS concept.

Technology is an important enabler to provide citizens with access to public and private real-time mobility services, even if MaaS has a strong orientation towards the implementation of new business models and requires new organisational concepts. Furthermore, the transparency of mobility costs can increase thank to technology. Many commonly applied transport-related process operations, even the most recent, are strongly related to technology, because the importance of its integration into mobility service planning and provision has increased. Examples of these operations are route planning, infrastructure/vehicle management, ticketing/pricing and booking.

The validation process in the demo site sites will enable a scientific and statistically sound analysis of the evaluation data, thus resulting in a specification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

6. Objective

IP4MaaS WP6 aims to assess the performance and impact generated by the project through COHESIVE demonstrations in relation with the overall project objectives and, after setting performance and impacts goals, to evaluate how they are met in the demonstrations.

The purpose of the document is to provide the assessment methodology to be applied to all demo sites for providing a common ground on evaluation activities. Different areas of assessment have been considered: performance, socio-economic and environmental impacts.

The assessment relies on inputs provided by the demo execution (WP5) and by the planning phase (WP4: Monitoring activities and WP3: KPI definition). The assessment methodology is composed by performance assessment and by impact assessment:

- Performance assessment collects all KPIs data gained from demo sites and User satisfaction Index (USIs) surveys. The creation of a dataset with KPIs data is the first step of performance assessment. The following step comprises the definition of algorithms for computational analysis. Afterwards, a selection of the most suitable methodological elements will be carried on in order to apply them within the dataset. The proper methodology to establish correlations and obtain conclusions on barriers and needs per each user group will be exposed. The last step regards the provision of methods for the calculation of the efficiency rate of each use-case (as defined in WP3).
- Impact assessment collects all KPIs data, affected by the actions carried out in demo sites framework, through ex-ante and ex-post analysis. The first step is to define and validate KPIs related to environmental, social and economic impact in the demonstrations. The second step consists in the selection of methodological elements aimed to assess the impact of the take-up of COHESIVE solutions at EU27 level. The last step of Impact assessment methodology defines a macro-model making use of elements derived both from literature and past projects and making use of Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA), Multicriteria Analysis (MCA).

7. Implementation steps of the evaluation process

The goal of Work Package 6 in the IP4MAAS project is to define and implement the overall evaluation methodology for assessing the impact generated by the project innovations at MaaS demo sites against the project's objectives. Performance and impact assessment will be accomplished to assess impacts in the mobility business sector as well as in the project sites, comparing ex-ante and ex-post situation. The assessment will rely on:

- **common evaluation methodology** based on relevant, complete, available, measurable and reliable KPIs to measure and assess socio-economic and mobility impacts of the MaaS offer;
- **direct measurements** provided by the deployed technical solutions.

The steps to perform the evaluation process are outlined in the followings.

7.1. Identification of type of data and target groups

The collection of data is an essential and critical task to the evaluation success. There are two types of data sources as pointed out in D3.2:

- **objective data** automatically collected within the software architecture and local systems (e.g. sensors, external platforms, etc.);
- **subjective data** collected by different methods that reflect the user's opinions (e.g. questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, in-app feedback, etc.).

For what concerns **objective data**, journey planner applications, for instance, enable to generate large amounts of data internally about all aspects of the service, including different types of data such as user requests, trip plans, status codes, etc. In large software projects where multiple parties are involved, some parts of these data sources are often provided via dedicated user interfaces in order to facilitate post-processing and various forms of visualization.

Interesting objective data to be automatically collected by the MaaS system are, in example, *the number of multimodal trips generated by journey planners connected to the MaaS scheme* and *the number of offers booked per day*; both indicators identify the success of a MaaS scheme in terms of user adoption.

For what concerns **subjective data**, they represent all the information collected from the users' opinions, comments and suggestions about the different aspects of the MaaS system (namely the "User Experience"). This input is essential to perform a valuable and meaningful evaluation. User experience feedback are all about subjective data dealing with the functionalities, results, usability and functioning as below:

- Functionalities: suggestions or improvements to add in the system.
- Results: wrong or incoherent results offered.
- Usability: difficulties to understand how the app works.
- Functioning: technical problems in the system functioning.

For subjective data, several communication channels need to be opened between the end-users and the demo sites managers to ensure the right collection of the feedback. Questionnaires may be collected only for real users and, in order to ensure that users fill out the questionnaires, each demo sites manager might consider to send reminders or set incentives to the list of participants to increase the rate of compiled questionnaires against to the total participants. The user

questionnaire should include firstly a background section dealing with information on the patterns and mobility behaviours of users; then it could be characterized by a set of questions to evaluate technical, usability and acceptance parts.

Also, face-to-face communications with test users might be applied if possible, in order to increase the submission rate as well.

Besides the types of data, it is relevant to well identify target groups concerned by project' actions. Four main target groups involved in MaaS development and operations can be considered as follows:

1. Individual / End-users (traveller-oriented)
2. Local Authorities (MaaS manager/promoter-oriented)
3. Private and public transport operators (MaaS participant/promoter-oriented)
4. ICT/ITS providers (MaaS developer/promoter-oriented)

Expected benefits of MaaS implementation are not only related to transport users' (citizens) but also to both the public sector and businesses.

For the public sector, MaaS development means improving the effectiveness of the whole transport system, efficient allocation of resources based on users' needs, reaching a more reliable and accessible transport system through advanced data deployment. On the other hand, public transport operators can benefit making easier to use public transport as part of the value chain and becoming the operators of new, seamless and user-oriented mobility.

For businesses, MaaS development means generating new business by profitable markets for new transport services, renewing opportunities for the traditional transport business sectors as part of innovative services concepts, providing smarter transport connections for all sectors.

Lastly, technology providers can benefit from the growth of this sector that could create new markets or enlarge existing ones (e.g. travel assistance services, territorial marketing applications, etc.).

Use cases and related evaluation activities aim at setting-up selected and segmented (in a balanced way in terms of main characteristics, background and geographical location) field tests and at assessing the IP4 solutions ensuring a full deployment and transferability of the application at EU level and beyond. For the multimodal operations and door-to-door transport information provision, smart and integrated ticketing (e.g. smartcards, mobile applications, etc.) as well as complete and integrated information (covering all available transport modes) are considered relevant key aspects. Provision of both pre-trip and on-trip information as well as individual and collective information should allow to increase intermodal journeys.

The IP4MAAS project aims at bringing concrete benefits to the four identified target groups by fulfilling its specific objectives stated in the Description of Action:

Specific Objective	Expected benefits for end-users and Local Authorities	Expected benefits for TSPs	Expected benefits for IP4 ecosystem
O1 - Design and develop a demonstration execution scheme tackling the		Demonstration monitoring through the measurement,	Technology mapping in WP2, measured by the number of Integrated

supervision of technical integration and demonstrations' management subjects		analysis and synthesis of selected KPIs and User Satisfaction Indexes	Technology Demonstrators (ITDs) and System Platform demonstrations
O2 - Execute co-creation and collaboration activities with demonstration stakeholders for demonstration planning and executing and for aligning the opinions of stakeholders on technology usage and integration		Co-creation actions addressing the concerns of stakeholders	Execution of co-creation actions generating information necessary for the project and increase information sharing between demo stakeholders
O3 - Monitor demonstrations of IP4 technologies in 6 different locations involving different transport operators.			Organisation and monitoring of demonstrations of IP4 technologies
O4 - Assess the realized demonstrations to determine the success of their execution and the level of satisfaction of users with the demonstrated technologies	Measurement of the level of user satisfaction with the implemented technology	Measurement of the level of TSP satisfaction with the implemented technology	

Table 1. List of operational KPIs per functionalities

7.2. Common criteria for selecting Key Performance Indicators

Indicators are measurements. They are an information that summarizes the characteristics of systems or highlights what is happening in a system. A more exhaustive definition is given by the International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD): "An indicator quantifies and simplifies phenomena and helps us understand complex realities. Indicators are aggregates of raw and processed data, but they can be further aggregated to form complex indices." Another exhaustive definition was given by the IMPROVERAIL, EC Funded Project: "Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are quantifiable measurements, agreed to beforehand, that reflect the critical success factors of a project. They will differ depending on the project but nevertheless they are quantitative and qualitative measures used to review an organization's progress against its goals. These are broken down and set as targets for achievement by departments and individuals"⁴.

According to OECD terminology, an indicator is "a parameter, or a value derived from parameters, which points to, provides information about, describes the state of a phenomenon /environment/area, with a significance extending beyond that directly associated with a

⁴ IMPROVE RAIL Deliverable 10 Project Handbook 2003

https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/project/documents/20060727_145926_44007_IMPROVERAIL_Final_Report.pdf

parameter value"⁵. Whatever KPIs are selected, they must reflect the project's objectives, they must be key to its success, and they must be measurable. KPIs usually are long-term considerations.

An in-depth analysis of KPIs was done in the IP4MAAS D3.2 deliverable per the two classes of data (objective and subjective). The resulting initial list of KPIs was submitted to IP4 and CFM for validation and during the evaluation process this list will be finalised, also including additional KPIs deriving from impacts assessment needs, as detailed in section 9.

While identifying KPIs, a robustness analysis was carried out by applying common criteria assuring correlation between strategic evaluation objectives, impacts and indicators as well as appropriateness of the data collection process. This in-depth analysis validated for all KPIs a minimum viable level for each of the following criteria:

- **Relevance:** each indicator must be an assessment criterion, in order to have a significant importance for the evaluation process for the selected event to be quantified/assessed.
- **Completeness:** the set of indicators must consider all aspects of the system/concept under evaluation.
- **Availability:** check if the indicator is existing on the ground and can be retrieved.
- **Measurability:** the identified indicators are structured in their definition/formula and can be measured objectively or subjectively.
- **Reliability:** indicators must be clear in their definition, easy to be aggregated and their measurements accurate.
- **Familiarity:** the indicators must be intuitive and easy to understand.
- **Non-redundancy:** indicators should not measure the same aspect of other indicators.
- **Independence:** small changes in the measurements of an indicator should not impact preferences assigned to other indicators of the evaluation framework.

Concerning KPIs preliminary identified for impact assessment (reported in 9.3.2), this robustness analysis will be further applied when finalising the list together with demo sites.

7.3. Evaluation process: assessing performances and impacts

The ability to evaluate whether the MaaS system induces behavioural changes towards more sustainable transport modes is critical to the measurement of targets described in the IP4MAAS Description of Action. Examples of KPIs dealing with **behaviour change** are listed as follows:

- Modal split of usage of available transport modes (% trips made by each transport mode)
- Decrease of usage of private cars (number of cars per inhabitants or total Km travelled by private car).

The evaluation process is also aimed at assessing the system's **impacts on mobility**. The majority of relevant KPIs should therefore be based on objective data and refer to the travel experience (namely to number of journeys, length and duration) and patterns (timing, mode, route). Examples of KPIs are listed as follows:

⁵ OECD, "OECD Environmental indicators – Development measurement and use", 2003

- Number of journeys undertaken per user (mean, mode and median number of trips made by users)
- Total journey time (duration of journey from start to destination)
- Daily average distance travelled (overall distance travelled per day per user)
- Mode of transport selected per user (% of trips made by each transport mode per user in each demo site).

These aspects of the evaluation process are targeted by the **performance assessment**, detailed in section 8.

On the other hand, it is important to highlight the **adoption rate** of the MaaS offer in IP4MAAS demo sites: being the project a demonstration action withing IP4 framework, it is not expected to reach a share that have statistical significance for what concerns the main environmental and socio-economic indicators listed above. For this reason, the **impact evaluation**, described in section 9, will complement the mere data collection, helping a sound evaluation by evidencing drivers and barriers of the implementation process and proposing an analysis of potential environmental, social and economic impacts in the longer term, when the MaaS uptake will be reached.

8. Performance assessment methodology

The performance assessment methodology will be based on several mathematical data analysis tools as detailed in the following subsections, which will be a Toolbox with separate modules executed sequentially with the aim to achieve relevant results about the performance of the Travel Companion APP in each demo site. See Figure 1 as a conceptual overview of the Toolbox, which will be developed in Task 6.2:

Figure 1. IP4MaaS assessment tools and modules

The *performance assessment toolbox* will work with data collected from *Operational KPIs* and *USIs surveys* in the WP5 during the execution of the demo.

Regarding Operational KPIs: Given that at this point, performance assessments will be done in a discrete way (one per each demo) instead of in a continuous pattern, the development of an API (application programming interface) for an automatic feed of this data from the TC APP regarding operational KPIs is not needed; alternatively, the data related to operational KPIs will be gathered through the cloud wallet shared by CFMs after each demo site.

Regarding data collected through USI surveys: The performance assessment toolbox will be automatically fed with data gathered through USI surveys programmed in Google Form. This process will be done in iterations. After the data collection of USI surveys on the first demo site, a new iteration will be done on the following demo sites. As a result, the toolbox assessment will manage the data analysis in six different pilots.

8.1. AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process)

8.1.1. The reason for applying the AHP method

The AHP is applied to get a weighted hierarchy of factors with an influence on the two following goals defined for users of the Travel Companion APP:

- I. For Travelers: To increase the number of Travelers on public transport, especially railways.
- II. For TSPs: To increase the acceptability of the Travel companion APP by TSPs.

8.1.2. How the AHP method works in performance analysis

The application of the AHP to the complex problem usually involves four significant steps (Cheng, Yang, & Hwang, 1999):

- I. Break down the complex problem into a number of small constituent elements and then structure the elements in a hierarchical form.
- II. Make pairwise comparisons among the elements according to a ratio scale.
- III. Use the eigenvalue method to estimate the relative weights of the elements.
- IV. Aggregate these relative weights and synthesize them for the final measurement of given decision alternatives.

8.1.3. The mathematical approach for the calculation of the weights through the matrix

AHP allows normalized local weights of alternatives to be calculated when compared with the third level criteria (w_{atk}) from the expert panel survey data. For calculation of normalized local weights (w_{atk}) of alternative “t” against criterion “k”, the following procedure was used:

1. The “n” criteria are compared in pairs for each level criteria using Saaty’s scale. These values form a comparison matrix A:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & 1 & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \text{ where } a_{ji} = 1/a_{ij} \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n$$

(Eq.1)

2. The consistency ratio (CR) (Eq. (2) of matrix A (Saaty T. , 1990) is used to check inconsistencies:

$$CR = \frac{(\lambda_{max} - n)/(n-1)}{RI}$$

(Eq.2)

Where “ λ_{max} ” is the larger or principal eigenvalue of matrix “A”, “n” is the size of the matrix and “RI” is the Random Index, which is an experimental value that depends on “n”

3. The local normalized weight of all criteria for a level “k” (w_{a1k} , w_{a2k} , w_{a3k} ,...) is the principal eigenvector of the pairwise comparisons matrix “A”, which is calculated by raising this matrix to a sufficiently large power:

$$q_{il}^z = \lim_{z \rightarrow \infty} A^z \quad (\text{Eq.3})$$

The process is stopped when the difference between “ w_{atk}^z ” obtained at the “zth” power and “ w_{atk}^{z+1} ” obtained at the (z + 1)th power is less than 10^{-4} .

$$w_{\text{atk}}^z = \frac{\sum_{l=1}^n q_{il}^z}{\sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{l=1}^n q_{il}^z} \quad (\text{Eq.4})$$

Moreover, it is especially relevant to obtain a value of the global normalized weight for each criterion versus the main goal that allows the issue to be addressed in a holistic way (W_{AtG}) was calculated as follows:

$$W_{CG_k} = w_{ci} \cdot w_{cj} \quad (\text{Eq.5})$$

Where w_{cj} , and w_{ci} are the local normalized weights for each criterion of the second and first levels. The AHP method applied to this case aims to identify aspects or factors influencing the Goals abovementioned, which are operational KPIs, and USI questions defined in D3.2; (IP4MaaS project (2022). Deliverable D 3.2 List of operational KPIs, analysis of the users’ satisfaction and methodology as a whole, F-REL) , and to define a weighted hierarchy of them. A hierarchical model in 2 levels for travelers (Figure 2) and another for TSPs (Figure 3) with these factors was generated and validated by a multidisciplinary panel (this validation process is still ongoing).

After this expert panel validates hierarchical models, pairwise comparison matrixes will be introduced. This means one pairwise comparison matrix per each criterion level 1. This comparison matrix will pairwise compare all criteria level 2 inside this criterion level 1.

The aim of preparing this matrix is to compare the importance between criteria levels 1 and 2. This matrix aims to assess the expert panel's technical opinion to determine which criteria are more important in achieving the main goal and how much this ratio is. (according to the scale of Saaty). The expert panel for the validation of the hierarchical models and the pairwise comparison between criteria influencing this goal is built in the following way (Reynolds, Schultz, & Hekman, 2006):

- One representant from each TSPs integrated with Athens's demo site phase I:
 - Katerina Antaraki, OASA
 - Marina Tampakidi, MIRAKLIO
 - George Keikoglou, BRAINBOX
 - Thodoros Stavridis, TAXIWAY
- 2 CFMs (software developers)
 - Souheir Mili, CS group
 - Marco Ferreira, Thales group
- 2 Associations
 - Giuseppe Rizzi, UITP

➤ Stefanos Gogos, UNIFE

Finally, the global weight of each criterion or factor influencing the goal will be calculated. This final global weight (Roy & Słowiński, 2013) will be calculated by multiplying the local weight of level 1 criteria and level 2 criteria calculated by applying AHP (Saaty T. , 2013).

Table 2. Scale of Saaty

Value	definition
1	Similar. Both elements are equally preferred.
3	The element in the row is slightly preferred.
5	The element in the row is strongly preferred.
7	The element in the row is very strongly
9	Extreme. The element in the row is extremely preferred.

Goal: To encourage people to use more intermodal solutions in public transport, especially railways, by making it more attractive to users.

Figure 2. Hierarchical model for travelers

Figure 3. Hierarchical model for TSPs

8.2. Bayesian network analysis and BELLMAN shortest path

8.2.1. The reason for applying the Bayesian network and Bellman

The computational methods employed for the data analysis include Bayesian network analysis to obtain a weighted hierarchy based on USI questionnaires and operational KPIs.

This method is applied for two reasons:

- Assess correlations between factors level 2 (see the hierarchical model in Figure 2 and Figure 3), encouraging people to use more intermodal solutions in public transport, especially railways, by making it more attractive to users (Saaty T. , 1990)
- Calculate a weighted hierarchy of these factors level 2 through the Bellman shortest pathway (see the following method) given the correlations defined in a). According to the hierarchical model, this weighted hierarchy of criteria level 2 will be compared with the weighted hierarchy obtained by applying only the AHP to validate results through these two methods: All AHP vs. AHP+BN. (Awad-Núñez, González-Cancelas, Soler-Flores, & Camarero-Orive, 2016)

8.2.2. How Bayesian network analysis and Bellman works in performance analysis

Regarding Bayesian network analysis: The K2 metric has been used (see Equation 6).

$$L = P(\mathbf{B}_S, \mathbf{D}) = P(\mathbf{B}_S) \cdot \prod_{i=1}^n \prod_{j=1}^{q_i} \frac{(r_i - 1)!}{(N_{ij} + r_i - 1)!} \cdot \prod_{k=1}^{r_i} N_{ijk}! \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

Where:

- $P(\mathbf{B}_S)$ is the probability of obtaining the network \mathbf{B}_S (initially all \mathbf{B}_S are considered to have the same probability, so $P(\mathbf{B}_S)$ is 1/number of possible networks).
- n is the number of variables.
- r_i is the number of possible values for each variable x_i .
- q_i is the number of possible configurations (given the network \mathbf{B}_S) of the variable x_i .
- N_{ij} is the number of times variable i adopts a specific configuration j . For example, if we consider a network \mathbf{B}_S Where the variable i has two parameters, N_{ij} This will be the number of times these parameters have the configuration j or specific values (e.g., 1 and 5). (Gámez, Mateo, & Puerta, 2011)
- N_{ijk} is the number of times that variable i adopts a specific value (e.g., 2) when the variables adopt the configuration j (e.g., 1 and 5). For example, when the two parameters' variables adopt values 1 and 5, variable i adopts 2 times the value 2. In this case, $N_{ijk}=2$.

Using the logarithmic expression in Equation (6), we obtained what we called the Bayes score, or K2 score (see Equation (7)). Using logarithmic expression and addition and subtraction operations results in computational run-time savings (Lerner & Malka, Investigation of the K2 algorithm in learning bayesian network classifiers. Applied Artificial Intelligence, 25(1), 2011).

$$\text{Bayes score} = \log[L] = \log(P(\mathbf{B}_S)) + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^{q_i} \left(\log \left(\frac{(r_i - 1)!}{(N_{ij} + r_i - 1)!} + \sum_{k=1}^{r_i} \log(N_{ijk}!) \right) \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

The Bayes score or K2 score can also be defined using the logarithmic gamma function (lgamma; see Equation (8)), which is easier to use in computation.

$$\text{Bayes score} = \log(P(\mathbf{B}_S)) + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^{q_i} \left((\text{lgamma}(r_i) - \text{lgamma}(N_{ij} + r_i)) + \sum_{k=1}^{r_i} \text{lgamma}(N_{ijk} + 1) \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

The main weakness of this K2 algorithm is the sensitivity to the initial order of nodes established by the user, a factor that can be reduced if an expert establishes the order. We introduced a high random number of iterations with different node orders to overcome this drawback. (Cooper & Herskovits, 1992)

Algorithms developed to automate this process were based on the Bayesian networks (BN) method presented by Cooper and Herskovits, which includes the K2 learning algorithm with the K2 score. The outputs obtained after this process were the Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG), which shows the interdependencies between the probability distribution of different variables or nodes considered in the analysis, and the Bayes score of the obtained DAG, which is a metric that measures the fitness of each structure to represent these interdependencies based on the database. (Lerner & Malka, Investigation of the K2 algorithm in learning bayesian network classifiers. Applied Artificial Intelligence, 2011)

8.2.3. Bellman shortest path

For each DAG, the Bellman-Ford algorithm was used to obtain the hierarchy of variables by automatically identifying the shortest path to the primary parameters for each node. The Bellman-Ford algorithm is a graph search algorithm to find the shortest route. Given a graph $G(V, E)$ (directed or undirected), where V is the set of vertexes and $E \subseteq (V \times V)$ is the set of edges, a source vertex S and a weight function $w: E \rightarrow R$, the Bellman-Ford algorithm visits G and finds the shortest path to reach the source vertex S by a vertex V , taking into account the weight function of edges from V to S . In our case, the weight function of each edge connecting the different nodes of the DAG is the K2 score, which is used to find the shortest paths from all vertexes V (nodes in \mathbf{B}_S) to a single source vertex S (primary parameters in \mathbf{B}_S). (Ekpanyapong, Waterwai, & Sung Kyu, 2006)

Figure 4 shows an example of a simple graphical representation of four nodes, made by the main parameters and three other vertexes, and the K2 scores associated with each arrow connecting the nodes. The distance of Vertex 3, according to the Bellman-Ford algorithm, would be:

Option A: Distance = K2 Score 4 + K2 Score 3, if K2 Score 3 is K2 Score 1 + K2 Score 2;

Option B: Distance = K2 Score 4 + K2 Score 1 + K2 Score 2 if K2 Score 3 > K2 Score 1 + K2 Score 2.

Figure 4. A graph with the K2 scores of each arrow connecting the different nodes (primary parameters and other vertexes) is a graphical example.

Importance of 10 is assigned to the BN(Bayesian Network) variable with the minimum distance and an importance of 1 to the BN variable with the maximum distance. A linear interpolation assigns the importance for the rest of variables. The weight of each variable is obtained by normalizing the importance assigned to each one in a way that the addition is 1 (Sulaiman, Siregar, Nasution, & Haramaini, 2018)

8.3. ANOVA test analysis

8.3.1. The reason for applying the ANOVA

In order to determine if some socio-demographic profiles are relevant for specific criteria, an ANOVA analysis was performed as a statistical way to compare different groups.

The ANOVA test for this case study will be done through the collected data from the USI questionnaire for travelers, and TSPs USI surveys will not be considered as they do not depend on socio-demographic profiles.

The USI survey was administered online to travelers who have to use different modes of transport from TSPs in the Athens demo site via an email containing a link to the survey via Google forms. A socio-demographic survey was part of this USI questionnaire for travelers.

8.3.2. How ANOVA works in performance analysis

In the ANOVA test, an assessment and analysis have been done based on the Level 2 criteria and the score (satisfaction level) in USI surveys. These level 2 criteria have been defined in the AHP method section.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) can be used as a marketer when we want to test a particular hypothesis. We would use ANOVA to help us understand how your different groups respond, with a null hypothesis for the test that the means of the different groups are equal. If there is a statistically significant result, then it means that the two populations are unequal (or different).

The ANOVA test in this study can help answer the following questions:

Do age, sex, income, profession, or other socio-demographic variables affect the satisfaction score regarding each Travel Companion functionality?

A factorial ANOVA can be used to answer this question since we have three independent variables and one dependent variable. We collected data for different socio-demographic groups. A two-way ANOVA can then simultaneously assess the effect of these variables on your dependent variable (spending) and determine whether they make a difference. (García, et al., 2021)

The mathematical approach to the ANOVA test has been defined as follows:

The statistical “F” that follows a Fisher distribution (Eq. 11) with a number of degrees of freedom equal to (df_{factor} , $df_{residual}$) is used for this analysis, where:

$$df_{residual} \text{ is:} \\ df_{residual} = (N-1) - df_{factor} \quad (\text{Eq.9})$$

Where,

N=total number of observations or total sample size

df_{factor} is the total number of groups (j) minus 1:

$$df_{factor} = (j-1) \quad (\text{Eq.10})$$

$$\text{“F” can be calculated as } F = \frac{MS \text{ factor}}{MS \text{ residual}} = \frac{\sum_j N_j (\mu_j - \mu)^2 / df \text{ factor}}{\sum_{ij} (x_{ij} - \mu_j)^2 / df \text{ residual}} \quad (\text{Eq.11})$$

Where:

μ =overall mean

μ_j =mean of group j

i=index of sample

j=index of group

x_{ij} = i^{th} sample from j^{th} group

The significance level α is the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis H_0 ($\mu_1 = \mu_2$) when it is true: In this case, the F (Fisher)-distribution has got a number of degrees of freedom equal to (df_{factor} , $df_{residual}$): F(1, 38), and the value F_0 for which $\alpha = 0,05$, what means a confidence level of 95%, is 4. If H_0 is true ($\mu_1 = \mu_2$), there is no statistical difference between samples and the probability that $F_0 > 4$ is 5% or less. Then if after the data collection and after calculating F according to Eq. 11, the value of F is higher than 4, we can conclude that the means of these 2 groups of study are different with a 95% of significance level (with an error of 5%).

Figure 5. Screenshot of the F distribution calculator

8.4. Regression analysis

8.4.1. The reason for applying the Regression analysis

While Bayesian Network analysis aims to reach a correlation among all variables in a network that will allow us to conduct statistical predictions, the Regression analysis seeks to identify pairwise correlations between these variables. These pairwise correlations between couples of variables will let us define fixed connections in the Bayesian Network analysis to get more accurate results. Scores for variables were collected through USI questionnaires launched through an online survey in Greek and English versions. A total of 21 questionnaires were collected (9 in the Greek version of the online survey and 12 in the English version).

8.4.2. How Regression analysis works in performance analysis

To understand regression analysis fully, it's essential to comprehend the following terms:

- I. Dependent Variable (Y): This is the main factor you're trying to understand or predict.

- II. Independent Variable (X): This is the factor you hypothesize impacts your dependent variable Y.

Regression works by using an independent variable to predict the values of the dependent variable. In a linear regression predictive model, the Equation (Eq.12) depicts the variations in the dependent variable Y from the given changes in the independent variable X. The expression is as follows:

$$Y = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X + \epsilon \quad (\text{Eq.12})$$

Where:

"Y" is the dependent variable,

"X" is the independent variable,

β_1 is the intercept, and β_2 is the slope, which are the two unknown constants that determine the predictive model.

ϵ is the error term (the difference between the observation and the predicted value of Y)

To calculate the values of parameters β_1 and β_2 , we need to solve the following algebraic equations simultaneously (Eq.13 and Eq.14):

$$-2 \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_i) = 0 \quad (\text{Eq.13})$$

$$-2 \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_i) \cdot X_i = 0 \quad (\text{Eq.14})$$

Being n=number of observations.

Linear Regression is one of the most basic machine learning algorithms that is used to predict a dependent variable based on one or more independent variables. The dependent variable (Y) should be continuous. If there is only one X variable, it is called 'Simple Linear Regression.' If more than one predictor (X) is involved, it is called 'Multiple Linear Regression.' Nevertheless, the procedure to build either of them is pretty much the same.

In regression analysis, three main elements should be identified:

T Statistic: the t value is the statistic metric calculated by dividing the beta coefficient (weight of the X variable) by its standard error S, where:

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \epsilon_i^2}{(n-2)}} \quad (\text{Eq.15})$$

So

$$t = \frac{\beta_2}{S} \quad (\text{Eq.16})$$

This T statistic follows a T probabilistic distribution with (n-1) freedom degrees.

P-value: Given a “t” value, the area at the right of this value in the T probabilistic distribution with (n-2) freedom degrees is the p-value. An independent variable X in the linear regression model is said to be statistically significant only if the p-value is less than a pre-determined statistical significance level, which usually is 0.05. This means that the weight of this independent variable X on the dependent variable Y is high (β_2 is high), and the error in the prediction is low (S is low).

R-Square: is a statistical measure that tells us the proportion of variation in the dependent (y) variable explained by different features (independent variables) in this model. Higher the value of R-Square, the better. The max it can go is 1.

9. Impact assessment

Outputs and outcomes of IP4 technologies application in the demo sites will be compared in order to carry out impact evaluation of the project solutions and methodologies.

In order to achieve reasonable potentials for replication, deployment, exploitation and scalability of the IP4MAAS solutions, in the project proposal expected targets have been delineated and they will be considered as guiding principles during the evaluation activities.

The behavioural change towards sustainable mobility modes, improving public transport offering, will be strengthened by IP4 technologies in demo sites and the extent of their application will be indicated by the evaluation methodology.

Regarding interrelated performances within economy, environment and society areas, the goal of impact assessment is to make a quantified evaluation of the direct effects of the methodologies and solutions developed within IP4MAAS project.

To assess whether the project will be a success or a failure, the main characteristics to consider are effectiveness and efficiency.

To enable a better interpretation of the results, a clear and concise evaluation must be provided, and the different demo sites have to coordinate the approaches, indicators and methods in order to achieve a higher level of comparability, which is fundamental for cross-site evaluation.

The first step to evaluate the impacts is the identification of stakeholder needs and objectives of the project, to figure out how they are connected to each other's. Afterwards, a check of this link can be done thanks to a selection of a set of indicators suitable to correlate objectives and targets aimed to be achieved by the project.

The targets of the project, grouped according with the evaluation objectives, are summarized in the following table.

1) Enrich the content of the demonstrations, by using real data, real processes, and potentially real environment for the demonstrations

Target 1 - At least 6 demonstrations	Target 2 - At least 900-1200 travellers involved in the conversational survey (about 150-200 per demo Site)	Target 3 - At least 50 descriptions of “travel experience (AS IS + TO BE)” scenarios (about 8-10 per demo Site)	Target 4 – At least 20 KPIs (per each demo site) for TSPs and travellers defined and monitored
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2) Demonstrate that the IP4 eco-system is versatile, able to face diverse environment, business rules, transport modes, and data standards

Target 5 - At least 20 partners and supporters (13 partners + 3 supporters) involved by transport operators and TSPs	Target 6 – At least 5,9 Million trips/year as potential overall demand (provisional figure)	Target 7 – At least 6 countries involved in demonstrations	Target 8 – At least 4 Modes of transport surveyed and subject of integration	Target 9 – At least 3 Sharing modes of transport involved	Target 10 – More than 10 Technologies and business models demonstrated against the application of IP4 technologies
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3) By bringing various stakeholders defining adequately the use-cases, the action will ease the market acceptance

Target 11 - At least 30 Participants to co-creation activities (about 5 stakeholders per demo site)	Target 12 - At least 20 Participants to stakeholder’s forum	Target 13 - At least 120 Participants to local stakeholder events	Target 14 – At least 50 Participants to the Final Event	Target 15 – At least 300 contacts per month through website
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4) Create the conditions of a successful deployment of the IP4 solutions

Target 16 - At least 4 Collaboration meetings with CFM projects	Target 17 - At least 200 Stakeholders (public and private) reached by the Transferability strategy (at EU-27 level)	Target 18 – More than 15 exploitation strategies and business models produced for TSPs
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Other relevant impacts

Other impact 1 - Contribution to complementary projects and other S2R projects	Other impact 2 - Contribution to S2R MAAP	Other impact 3 - Contribution to EU policies	Other impact 4 - Competitiveness of rail, public transport and ICT industry, SMEs and job creation	Other impact 5 - Environmental impact	Other impact 6 - Social and geographical cohesion
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Table 3: Expected impacts and targets of IP4MAAS project

The targets above-presented take in account the assumption that a relevant share of the population is aware about MaaS schemes and favourable to adopt this mobility model.

The structure of the assessment approach is based on the following elements:

- **Data logs:** the various software that manage the processes record and store these data
- **Evaluation forms:** In demo sites questionnaires, to be filled in by the actors involved, regarding KPIs with pre-set answers are going to be proposed.

The direct effects of IP4 technologies within environmental and socio-economic areas will be evaluated by the impact assessment. Specifically, the evaluation areas considered are:

- **Environmental area:** pollution and GHG emissions
- **Socio-economic area:** Economy, quality of service, benefits, acceptance, accessibility, security.

The main characteristic of impact assessment is the application of an ex-ante and ex-post analysis, that is the comparison between the initial situation before the beginning of the demo sites, and the future situation characterized by the use of IP4 technologies.

For this reason, WP2 deliverables will define the “**baseline situation**” of the demo sites thanks to relevant data and in WP5 the IP4 technologies and IP4MAAS solutions will be tested.

Therefore, impact assessment helps to split the impacts derived from IP4MAAS solutions from what is caused by other external circumstances. When an interrelated performance is assessed, the outputs and the outcomes directly related to IP4MAAS must be defined.

The **outputs** are physical appearance of the activities.

The **outcomes** are the measurable or perceived impacts that such a physical appearance have.

Data collection is the backbone of Impact evaluation. Information about indicators is provided by the analysis, which depends by the data collected, specifically, by the type of information needed according with the indicators. To collect these data in the correct way, different **methods of data collection** (measurements) can be chosen:

- a) Direct measurement using instrumentation (including specific software and/or simulation tools)
- b) Direct observation or recording of events within the demo sites
- c) Surveys by:
 - Questionnaire

- Interviews
- Diary completion

d) Collection from historical records

e) Use of focus groups and stakeholder meetings.

In order to be suitable for impact assessment, indicators must fill all the following characteristics:

- what data is to be collected (performance indicator and measurement unit),
- when data is to be collected (frequency of measurement),
- where the data is to be collected (domain for measurement),
- how the data is to be collected (method of measurement),
- from whom data is to be collected (target group for measurement),
- which is the level of actual and expected value of data.

When a measure regards counts, measurement, or other physical units it is referred as **quantitative data**.

When a measure regards perceptions and/or observations, people’s attitudes, that is uncountable figures that can be ordered by “nominal” scale (simple classification data, categorical scales), “ordinal” scale (subjective scales data gathered from measurement) or “evaluative” scales (requiring the assignment of a numerical value), we are talking about **qualitative data**.

The table below lists the variables composing the KPIs used into the framework.

Variables for KPIs	
Variables	Description
Performance indicator ID number	A unique ID number has been assigned to the KPIs
Performance indicator name	This is the name assigned to the KPIs
Performance indicator definition	This is the description of the KPIs
Measurement unit	This indicates the measurement unit defined for each KPI
Method of measurement	This is a quantitative/qualitative mean of calculation defined for each KPI
Target Group for measurement	This identifies the target group category providing the KPI
Project’s Objective	This correlates the KPI with the correspondent project objectives that it affects
IP4MaaS impact target	This correlates the KPI with the correspondent impact target that it affects

Table 4: Variables composing the KPIs

9.1. Definition of the Macro-model

Once the approach to collect and validate the KPIs is defined, the methodology for the macro-model, on which the cross-site evaluation is based, can be presented.

The main goal is to give a measurable value to the resulting benefits obtained thanks to the use of IP4 technologies within the demo sites. For this purpose, some elements derived by Cost-Benefits

Analysis (CBA) methodology can be applied.

The methodology used for CBA is based on the general guidelines set and recommended by the *Guide to Cost-Benefit Analysis of Investment Projects Economic appraisal tool for Cohesion Policy 2014-2020, European Commission (2014)*⁶.

CBA is functional tool which allows to assess the impacts of a certain project or product on various aspects, as environment, society or transport. Specifically, CBA helps to attribute benefits and economic costs. Therefore, to make explicit the socio-economic point of view, CBA aims to carry out an assessment of the economic viability.

In this context, the goal is to observe the benefits led to each demo site by the introduction of IP4MAAS solutions, analysing benefits deriving from the improvement of accessibility and competitiveness of Rail and public transport, ICT industry, SMEs, job creation as well as the improvement of environmental impact, social and geographical cohesion, contribution to EU policies. The impacts of IP4 technologies in the demo sites will be assessed and the benefits will be calculated for all the actors involved: end-users, local authorities, public and private transport operators.

In IP4MAAS two scenarios are assumed:

- "Baseline", this is the baseline scenario, identified by all the AS-IS use cases, that is without the support of IP4 technologies
- "Project", given by the introduction of IP4 technologies in the MaaS scheme of each demo site, that is the TO BE use cases in which the contribution of IP4MAAS solutions is evaluated.

The elements taken from the CBA methodology are needed in order to give monetary values to the benefits and costs of each scenario, to compare them and then assess if the "project" scenario is more convenient and attractive than the "baseline" scenario.

The economic point of view allows to compare indicators hard to quantified (e.g., social impacts, contribution to policy goals) and to report them with measurable costs and benefits (e.g. expected revenue, operation costs).

Given the limited time interval passing between Baseline and Project scenario, only the indicators subject to measurable variations will be elaborated with CBA elements.

Therefore, the following stages are foreseen:

- **Ex ante and ex post benefits' analysis:** in this stage, the identification, validation and monetization of the benefits of both scenarios is performed, before (ex-ante) and after (ex-post) the IP4MAAS solutions implementation.
- **CAPEX and OPEX identification:** in this stage, the identification of investments costs (CAPEX – CAPital EXpenditure) and operations costs (OPEX – Operational EXpenditure) is performed for each scenario.
- **Costs and benefits comparison:** in the final stage, there is the comparison of costs and benefits between "baseline" and "project" scenarios. Thanks to the monetization, each

⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy, Economic Appraisal Vademecum 2021-2027, https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docgener/guides/vademecum_2127/vademecum_2127_en.pdf

scenario will have a final value R_i (Revenue), given by the difference between B_i (Benefits) and C_i (Costs)

$$R_i = B_i - C_i \quad (\text{Eq.15})$$

where i can be the “baseline” or the “project” scenario and both B and C are, for each scenario, respectively the sum of all the monetary values coming from the benefits and the costs.

Focusing on the last stage, a fundamental step is the assessment of monetary values. Specifically, this passage foresees that, for every KPI measurement unit which will be calculated, a unit monetary value is assigned. It is possible to carry out this step thanks to a list of **conversion factors**, which allow to guide toward a coherent monetary conversion of numeric variables (e.g., number of trips, emission reductions, number of tickets) and unmeasurable variables (e.g., quality of service, attitudes toward PT and other sharing means of transport, travel experience). Usually, the conversion factors are taken by literature, studies, or other similar projects. In case of difficulties to find such conversion factors for some indicators, they will be elaborated together with the involved stakeholders of each demo site during validation phase.

After the assignment of measurable values to each benefit/cost related to the demo sites implementation, the goal is to elaborate a process aimed to rank and weight the obtained results, in order to develop an efficient cross-site evaluation.

To evaluate the consequences and the different effects (direct and indirect) on the travellers and on TSPs, a methodology which recalls the Multi-Criteria Analysis will be used.

Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) is a support tool for cross-comparisons, improving the efficiency of the evaluation process and allowing, in a nutshell:

- to define a hierarchical scale of possible alternatives and their different combinations
- to organically synthesize the opinions expressed by the various players in the evaluation process with regards to subjective data.

The MCA allows to evaluate in a comparative way criteria and indicators that can be expressed in objective and subjective terms, such as number of travel solutions shown and user satisfaction of the Journey Planner.

The MCA is based on the construction of an evaluation matrix which reports, for each demo site examined, the value of each objective to which the criterion and indicator is underlying. Subsequently, by combining this matrix with the weights attributed to each criterion and indicator, it is possible to obtain a ranking of the examined KPIs, thus an impact assessment supporting objective evaluation of pros and cons per each demonstration carried out.

The following diagram summarizes the logical process according to which the MCA is structured.

Figure 6: Logic scheme of MCA

In this MCA, we therefore proceed by identifying the evaluation criteria and then proceed to the attribution of the weights, using elements of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method. The method is based on the values and judgments expressed by individual decision makers regarding the (relative) importance of the various possible objectives pursued by an intervention or a mobility solution.

In particular, the AHP allows, once defined the criteria that fully express the objectives of the choice between alternatives (in our cases alternative are the different KPIs to be compared), to attribute the importance of each criterion through the participation of potentially interested stakeholders through the "comparison in pairs". This method consists in the pairwise evaluation of the criteria in order to arrive at the definition of a value function that aggregates the preferences of the stakeholders and allows an ordering of importance of the criteria by means of the results of the comparisons suitably elaborated.

A fundamental and characteristic element of the AHP is the scale of relative importance of the criteria, which will be used for the comparison in pairs.

The subsequent steps of the MCA allow the classification of KPIs through the steps of assigning the values of the indicators, the weighting of the scores for the importance of each indicator and criterion (or the importance they assume for the surveyed decision makers), and the definition of a summary ranking of the KPIs results.

The peculiar element of the different approaches to MCA is the aggregation function that allows the attribution of a synthetic score to each site and the formulation of a ranking of sites. In this MCA, the simplest aggregation function will be used, namely the "weighted sum", which is rendered by the expression

$$X_i = \sum_j \pi_j x_{ij}$$

(Eq.16)

In other words, X_i is the same of B_i of eq. 15, but with the ponderation of all the monetary values calculated for the benefits specified.

9.2. Measurement process of impact assessment

Since KPIs methodology as well as the macro-model for the cross-site evaluation have been defined, now the measurement process can be presented. The first step of the measurement process is the selection of the KPI's in each demo site according with the availability of the data. The aim is to have a minimum and representative number of KPIs in each demo site, according with the robustness process described in section 7. Furthermore, to obtain a more robust cross-site evaluation, the goal is to have more KPIs in common possible between demo sites. The result will be a reduced and site-based matrix of KPIs able to properly reflect the local evaluation plan for each demo site based upon the respective local conditions, taking in account the IP4MAAS solutions that they will finally test in WP5. At this stage, the choice of KPIs by demo sites is still to be done. It will occur at the end of 2022, and it will be discussed in deliverable D6.3. In the section 9.3, the six demo sites are presented. After an overview of the location, the characteristics and the actors involved, a general list of proposed KPIs is presented, from which each demo sites will create its own site-based matrix. Finally, a brief list of recommendations for data collection and validation concludes this section.

9.3. Demo sites KPIs

Six demonstrations sites have been deployed in order to facilitate and coordinate IP4 technologies demonstrations, which propose offers of seamless experiences of multimodal travel. The IP4 technologies employed in IP4MAAS project allow to address cases of commuters, tourist and other users who would be attracted to public and shared transport services. The six demonstration sites will be deployed in two different contexts: urban (Barcelona, Athens and Warsaw) and rural (Padua, Liberec and Osijek).

9.3.1. Overview of demo sites

Barcelona

The location of the demo Site is Barcelona metropolitan area, in Spain, including urban and suburban areas. The available transit opportunities cover a distance of 23-50km, from the city centre of Barcelona to medium sized cities. The TSPs involved are:

- **TMB**, which is the main public transport operator and operates metro and several bus lines in the urban metropolitan area
- **BusUp**, which uses a booking platform to link bus operators and its customers for ride-sharing services and on demand services
- **AMTU**, which is a MaaS operator and a transport operator who developed demand responsive system and the correlate application

- **SocialCar**, which is sharing and car renting company with the main role to cover first mile and last mile allowing travellers to reach and use public transport services. Social Car will not be integrated in the ecosystem but will be involved in the demo supporting the leader, as per amendment 1 submitted and accepted in August-September 2022.

The demo aims, though the reduction of vehicles and an improvement of people communication for travelling from home to different locations with share modes, to optimize the use of multi-modal travel thanks to IP4 ecosystem.

The achievement of shared mobility solution for peripheral urban areas and a unique seamless journey as well as the development of individual mobility offers and services are the main expectations for the demo Site of Barcelona.

Two main use-cases will be deployed: a) Same starting point - different destination, about people who live in a village, residential area nearby Barcelona but work in Barcelona, in different destinations; b) Different starting point - same destination, focused on people working for the same company, which is located in a relatively remote location.

Athens

The location of the demo site is Athens urban areas, Greece. The TSPs involved are:

- **OASA**, which is an urban public transport and MaaS operator
- **TrainOSE**, which manages the suburban railway
- **Taxiway**, which is a taxi company
- **BrainBox**, which is a bike sharing service and a tourist transport provider; **MIRAKLIO**, which is the municipal PT service operator.

The demo aims to deploy a single application that, through integrated ticketing and journey planning, allows to enhance multimodality.

The reconfiguration of the MaaS provider services using knowledge about user needs will be the main expected impact. The identification of mobility patterns, the combination of modes and the localisation of transport services places will be the instruments to collect significant data.

Three main use-cases will be deployed: 1) Multimodal work trip Case 1, from central Athens to any other metro station outside central area; 2) MaaS for tourists Case 2, from Pireaus Port to any other metro station; 3) Rural - urban interfaces Case 3 – From central Athens to any other metro station or site, both for work and shopping/leisure trips.

The identification of mobility patterns, the combination of modes and the localization in which transport services should be provided will be the instruments to collect demo data for the neutral mobility platform

Warsaw

The location of the demo site is Warsaw metropolitan area, Poland. The TSPs involved are:

- **MIASTO WARSZAWA**, which is the coordinator of PT services for the municipality; **MZA**, which is municipal bus operator
- **TRAM WARSAW**, which is the tramway operator.

The demo aims to assess all services and IP4 functionalities under the IP4MaaS project, including user profiling, ticketing, travel reports or MaaS schemes.

The implementation of MaaS principles and the improvement of the entire ecosystem, specifically its technological platform are the main expected impacts. To reflect currently ongoing organizational and social changes in Warsaw, the demo will be focused on different types of mobility, integrated by public transport nodes.

Padua

The location of the demo site is Padua urban & suburban areas and Veneto Region, Italy. The TSPs involved are:

- **Trenitalia**, which is the national railway operator
- **Bus Italia**, which is a bus company.

The demo aims to spread new mobility management services to individual passengers as well as city administrations, companies and universities through the digitalization of multiple mobility services managed by FSI train and bus operators. Furthermore, the demo goal is the integration of all mobility options available throughout the Padova Region into mobility packages which consider specific requirements of citizens daily activities.

The improvement of mobility planning and management services of the Ferrovie dello Stato Group and the offer to institutional customers of new services through the integration of IP4 technical features will be the main expected impacts.

Liberec

The location of the demo site is Liberec Region and the Czech Republic, likely including to the entire area of Borderland CZ/D/PL comprising Liberec, Zittau and Bogatynia regions. The TSPs involved are:

- **KORID**, which is the regional Transport Authority
- **ČSAD Liberec**, which is the local PTO and school-bus operator
- **ARRIVA vlaky**, the main railway operator.

The demo aims to involve other local PTOs, cross-border regional authorities, municipalities and ridesharing (BlablaCar) services.

The improvement of services provided by the dispatching centre and the overcoming of barriers to cross-border ticketing unification are the main expected impacts.

Five main use-cases will be deployed, regarding different user segments, paths and destinations.

Osijek

The location of the demo site is Osijek-Baranja County, Croatia. The TSPs involved are:

- **GPP Osijek**, which is the PTO managing tram and bus urban transport
- **HŽ Putnički prijevoz**, which is the national railway operator.

The demo aims: to test and demonstrate S2R IP4 functionalities by connecting different current back-end systems and providing added value to PT users; to test and demonstrate Journey planning, My trips, and Navigation and Location Based services with current PT services and new services currently in implementation; to utilize potential new functionalities for unified ticketing with railway passenger operator systems; to explore business analytics across different PT services

portfolio.

A more integrated, easier-to-use and open system for better customer experience, seamless ticketing and multimodal services for one of the largest students' populations in Croatia (target group for innovative transport testing) is the main expected impact.

9.3.2. Proposed KPIs

In the following table a list of KPIs is proposed. At this stage (methodology's presentation) no validation has been done with the demo sites yet. Therefore, this is a complete list of the possible KPIs that will be improved and standardized according with demo sites needs and expectations. To make clear the correlation between the KPIs and the project's objectives⁷ as well as with the impact targets, the last two columns of the table show these links.

ID	Indicator name	Indicator definition	Measurement unit	Method of measurement	Target Group	Evaluation areas	Project's Objective	IP4MaaS impact target
1	Increase of capacity of railway segments	% Increase the capacity of railway segments to meet increased demand for passenger and freight railway services compared to "State-of-the-art" 2014	%	Data from Local Authorities and Public bodies	TSPs, Local Authorities	Socio-Economic	Objective 1	Other Impact 4
2	CFMs Members	All partners TSPs have been successfully onboarded by CFMs.	number	Survey	TSPs	Socio-Economic	Objective 1	Target 5

⁷ Project's Objective 1: Design and develop a demonstration execution scheme tackling the supervision of technical integration and demonstrations' management subjects.

Project's Objective 2: Execute co-creation and collaboration activities with demonstration stakeholders for demonstration planning and executing and for aligning the opinions of stakeholders on technology usage and integration.

Project's Objective 3: Monitor demonstrations of IP4 technologies in 6 different locations involving different transport operators.

Project's Objective 4: Assess the realized demonstrations to determine the success of their execution and the level of satisfaction of users with the demonstrated technologies.

ID	Indicator name	Indicator definition	Measurement unit	Method of measurement	Target Group	Evaluation areas	Project's Objective	IP4MaaS impact target
3	Local dissemination events	Number of participants in local events	numbers	Data from demo sites	Stakeholders and users	Socio-Economic	Objective 2	Targets 11-12-13-14-17
4	Number of meetings	Multiple meetings between each demo site and CFMs facilitated by IP4MaaS	numbers	Data from demo sites	TSPs demo sites	Socio-Economic	Objective 3	Targets 11-12-13-14-16-17
5	Quality of service	Perception of quality of service	Qualitative index	Survey	End-users Private and public transport operators	Socio-Economic	Objective 4	Target 2
6	Attitudes towards PT, sharing, etc.	Number of persons declaring their opinion about the different modes of transport	Qualitative index	Survey	End-users Local Authorities	Socio-Economic	Objective 4	Other Impact 4
7	Employment	Additional number of jobs that is the consequence of the MaaS system	numeric	Survey	Local Authorities Private and public transport operators	Socio-Economic	Objective 1	Other Impact 4
8	New standard or regulations	Impact to standards and regulations related to multimodality, integrated ticketing, etc.	Qualitative index	Data retrieved by the demo sites actors	Private and public transport operators TSPs	Socio-Economic	Objective 2	Other Impact 3

ID	Indicator name	Indicator definition	Measurement unit	Method of measurement	Target Group	Evaluation areas	Project's Objective	IP4MaaS impact target
9	Governance model	Impact to public-private regulations governing urban transport services	Qualitative index	Data retrieved by the demo site actors	Local Authorities Private and public transport operators TSPs	Socio-Economic	Objective 2	Other Impact 3
10	Total Trips	Total number of trips made	Number	Data recorded from Software platform	End-users	Socio-Economic Environmental	Objective 3	Target 6
11	Transport Modal shift	% of trips made by each transport mode	%	Data recorded from Software platform	End-users	Socio-Economic Environmental	Objective 2	Target 8
12	Travel experience	Description and opinions on efficiency of the journey	Quality index	Survey	End-users	Socio-Economic	Objective 1	Target 3
13	Daily average distance	Overall distance travelled per day per user	Km	Data recorded from Software platform	End-users	Socio-Economic Environmental	Objective 3	Other Impact 6
14	Geographical position	Identification of starting points and ending points	GPS coordinates	Data recorded from Software platform	End-users	Socio-Economic	Objective 3	Other Impact 6

ID	Indicator name	Indicator definition	Measurement unit	Method of measurement	Target Group	Evaluation areas	Project's Objective	IP4MaaS impact target
15	User segments	Type of users according with age, gender or their characteristics (men/women, young/old, ...)	Numeric, %	Survey	Private and public transport operators TSPs	Socio-Economic	Objective 2	Target 2
16	CO2 emissions	CO2 per vkm by type	G/vkm	Derived by measurements	End-users Local Authorities	Environmental	Objective 3	Other Impact 5
17	CO emissions	CO per vkm by type	G/vkm	Derived by measurements	End-users Local Authorities	Environmental	Objective 3	Other Impact 5
18	NOx emissions	NOx per vkm by type	G/vkm	Derived by measurements	End-users Local Authorities	Environmental	Objective 3	Other Impact 5
19	Particulate emissions	PM10 and/or PM2.5 per vkm by type	G/vkm	Derived by measurements	End-users Local Authorities	Environmental	Objective 3	Other Impact 5
20	CO levels	CO concentration	Ppm or g/m3	Derived by measurements	End-users Local Authorities	Environmental	Objective 3	Other Impact 5

ID	Indicator name	Indicator definition	Measurement unit	Method of measurement	Target Group	Evaluation areas	Project's Objective	IP4MaaS impact target
21	NOx levels	NOx concentration	Ppm or g/m3	Derived by measurements	End-users Local Authorities	Environmental	Objective 3	Other Impact 5
22	Particulate levels	Particulate PM10 and/or PM2.5 concentration	Ppm or g/m3	Derived by measurements	End-users Local Authorities	Environmental	Objective 3	Other Impact 5
23	Collaboration / partnership in value chain	Number of public and private operators (transport service providers) cooperating in the MaaS offering	Numeric	Data retrieved by the demo site actors	Private and public transport operators	Socio-Economic	Objective 2	Target 18
24	IT interoperability	Number of data exchange processes among operators (transport providers, IT operators, etc.) in the MaaS scheme	Numeric	Data retrieved by the demo site actors	Private and public transport operators TSPs	Socio-Economic	Objective 2	Target 15

ID	Indicator name	Indicator definition	Measurement unit	Method of measurement	Target Group	Evaluation areas	Project's Objective	IP4MaaS impact target
25	Availability of interconnection information	Availability of information for connecting with other PT modes/means of transport Multimodal information (incl. service disruptions and emergency info) according to user needs	Qualitative index	Survey	Local Authorities Private and public transport operators TSPs	Socio-Economic	Objective 2	Target 8
26	Interoperability between MaaS and Journey Planners	Number of Journey Planners provided by or connected to the MaaS operator platform	Numeric	Data retrieved by the demo site actors	Private and public transport operators TSPs	Socio-Economic	Objective 1	Target 15
27	Integrated ticketing	Number of tickets for any urban trip (PT, taxi, car sharing, etc.) sold via the integrated ticketing channel out of the total	%	Data recorded from Software platform	Private and public transport operators TSPs	Socio-Economic	Objective 3	Target 15

ID	Indicator name	Indicator definition	Measurement unit	Method of measurement	Target Group	Evaluation areas	Project's Objective	IP4MaaS impact target
28	Multimodal Integrated ticketing	Number of ticket involving more than one mode of transport sold via the integrated ticketing channel out of the total	%	Data recorded from Software platform	Private and public transport operators TSPs	Socio-Economic	Objective 4	Target 18
29	Financial accessibility	Availability of discount tickets or passes for specific target groups of people	Qualitative index	Survey	End-users Local Authorities	Socio-Economic	Objective 4	Other Impact 4
30	Ancillary Services	Number of additional services (parcel delivery, long distance trip booking, mobility management and/or loyalty programs and other facilities linked to urban travels) offered besides the MaaS scheme	Numeric	Data retrieved by the demo site actors	Private and public transport operators TSPs	Socio-Economic	Objective 4	Target 18

Table 5: List of proposed KPIs

9.3.3. Recommendations for data collection and validation

The KPIs proposed for demo sites have been chosen taking in account the feasibility of measurement. Furthermore, the proposition of a package with few but specific KPIs is aimed to narrow the variability of KPIs among the demo sites, then to increase the possibility to obtain common tools for cross-sites evaluation.

Looking at the methods of measurement of various KPIs, there are 4 ways to obtain the data:

- 8 KPIs will be directly retrieved by demo sites actors and within the demo sites framework
- 6 KPIs will be measured by software platforms and will report the effective usage of MaaS offer
- 8 KPIs will be derived by measurement campaigns
- 8 KPI will be derived by surveys administrated to end-users and TSPs

Considering that the user experience will vary from the ex-ante to the ex-post situation, the impact assessment will be set-up as follows:

- a) As is: to measure each KPIs before the demo sites start to implement IP4 technologies, in order to have a clear vision of the current state-of-art
- b) To be: to measure each KPIs after the demo sites start and during all their duration, in order to assess the IP4 technologies impacts and then evaluate the improvements achieved due their contribution

This desktop measurement procedure will be repeated enough times in order to have stable values.

The actors involved in the data collection procedures will be:

- End-users
- Private and public transport operators
- Local Authorities
- TSPs

10. Conclusions

This deliverable presented the overall methodology designed for the evaluation process of IP4MAAS project.

In order to address the evaluation problem in such a complex environment, working with project partners, CFMs, external stakeholders and users, two different and complementary approaches were proposed and elaborated: performance assessment and impact assessment.

Both elements of the methodology are fully prepared and evaluation work is already in progress, having already outlined, and in some cases validated, preliminary KPIs.

In the next period the work will continue by:

- Completing and validating KPIs list for both performance and impact assessments;
- Start KPIs collection according to demo sites activities.

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